

THE NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES OF THE GREAT MASSACRE ON UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article covers the dire consequences of the colonial policy that Soviet power carried out in our country. During this period, the most educated, educated people of their time and people with a kata reputation in society became victims of a great massacre.

Key words: great massacre, Soviet government, freedom of the motherland, despotic regime, Siberia, Ukraine, North Caucasus, Urals, glaciers. Far East, Caucasus and Volga region, NKVD, Algiers.

The result of the rapid development of industry on a global scale is observed the change in the weather. Huge glaciers located in the northern part of the Earth's surface are increasingly melting and retreating. This is the reason for the rise of the water SATX. It is necessary to awaken a sense of patriotism in them first of all in the development of akholin as an active citizen, waking up from the sleep of ghaflat. In turn, we need to arm citizens, especially the growing younger generation, with the truth of history in instilling a sense of respect for the motherland. Consequently, looking at our statehood, which has a rich history of almost three thousand years, we can see that in this davir range our ancestors went through many invasions and struggles. The end of these invasions was the Russian Kingdom and Soviet power, which for 130 years conquered and colonized our country.

The Soviet government, which came to power from October 1917, pursued a colonial policy in the country until 1991. As a result of the colonial policy of Soviet power for 74 years, many of the country's selfless people were killed as a result of a massive massacre. Soviet power, which fought against the rational actions of yurtarian and Justicialist people in the eyes of the core, were those who were fully interested in the destruction of these people. After all, it was not for them that large extermination work was carried out from the colonizers, and today we would have achieved the development of the Uzbek state in the bundan. In this regard, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward the following points; "these people were real leaders, progressive intellectuals, figures of literature, culture, in other words, the most famous representatives of our nation, our people. Imagine what great things they would have done if they had not been repressed — for the development of our motherland, for science, economy, culture and literature-would have started our people-ahead. The same has been learned. Today we will remember this with dream"¹.

Indeed, the sacrifice of the representatives of the intelligentsia of our people, who acted for the freedom and well-being of the motherland, as a result of a great massacre, was a big blow to the growth of such olumu fuzalos and statesmen as Imam Bukhari, Akhmad Al Khorezimi,

¹ Аъзамхўжаев С. Ўзбекистоннинг давлат мустақиллиги эълон қилинганидан сўнг тарихий ҳақиқат ва адолатни тиклаш бўйича олиб борилган ишлар энг аввало, Ватан ва халқ озодлиги йўлида жонини фидо этган ватандошларимиз хотирасини абадийлаштиришда намоён бўлди. // <https://religions.uz/news/detail?id=1490>

Ibn Sina, Akhmad al Fergani, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Zakhriddin Muhammad Babur, etc. The dire consequences of the qata massacre policy pursued by the Savet government Yanna were such that in some way this policy was also a heavy duty for us to step into the third Renaissance era, which is being promoted today by our president and which we dream of.

Efforts to name the March sons of the land who did not even return to sacrifice their lives on the path of independence and liberation without bowing to the colonists on the path of liberation of the motherland and the eternal preservation of their pure zinc began in our country from the early days of independence. On August 31, 2002, the museum "memory of victims of repression" was opened on the territory of the memorial complex "memory of martyrs", founded in the Yunusabad District of Tashkent City with the condolences of the brinci President Islam Karimov, in order to honor the memory of the devotees who fought for freedom and independence and did not spare their lives.

In turn, in addition to honoring the memory of the victims of repression, attention was paid to a more in-depth study of their scientific heritage, and on October 8, 2020, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5598 "on further measures to further study the heritage of victims of repression and perpetuate their memory" became the basis for In this decree, it was noted that the colonial policy of the Soviet government carried out in our country .

In particular, according to this decree, "research works, artistic and documentary works are being created aimed at identifying the names of our compatriots who were unjustly sacrificed during the years of political repression, studying the legacy left by them and bringing it to the general public.

The urgent task remains to perpetuate the names and memories of state and public figures, representatives of science, culture and art, literature, thousands of compatriots of ordinary professions, to educate our young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to our motherland and people on the example of their courage and perseverance. An impartial and truthful study of historical information in this regard serves to a deeper understanding of how hard and hard the independence of our country was achieved, how to live our today's free, free and prosperous life, preserving and appreciating it."²

The colonial policy of the Soviet government, which the old man spent 74 years in our country, seemed to marry the prosperity and peace of the ring more than one could bring, but the tak ground of this policy provided for the holding of the Uzbek ring in fear and muteyism. Deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan Abdumalik Akramov, Tursunoy Muratova, who reflected in their articles the disgusting and severe consequences of such a policy of the despotic regime, provided the following tariff:

"During the time of the despotic regime, the lives of thousands of our innocent compatriots were in vain. In 1937-1953, 100 thousand people were repressed in Uzbekistan. 13 thousand of them were brutally shot. How many families are honoured, and the children are orphaned. During the Great Repression of 1937-38 alone, about 7 thousand of our compatriots were shot.

²Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг фармойиши. Катагон қурбонларининг меросини янада чуқур ўрганиш ва улар хотирасини абадийлаштиришга доир кўшимча чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида. // <https://lex.uz/docs/5041012>

According to some reports, about two million of our compatriots have left Turkestan, leaving for foreign countries. 1 million 700 thousand compatriots were transported to Siberia, Ukraine, the North Caucasus, the Urals, Kazakhstan, the Far East, the Caucasus and the Volga region.

Among them were the well-known enlightenment people who could stand up for freedom, the figures of the Jadid movement, Germany, Turkey, and even people of various professions who, having studied in the leading higher educational institutions of Russia, were determined to serve for the good of the nation.

This regime not only repressed themselves those who fell into the "black list", but also subjected their family members to suffering. In particular, for the women of the "enemy of the people", a camp was organized in Karaganda called "Aljir" (Akmolinsky camp jyon izmennikov rodini), whose children were distributed to orphanages in different regions of the former Union.

According to the data, by Order of the NKVD No. 00486, 6,500 women from "family members of the traitors of the motherland" served in "Aljir" in 1938-1946. Children of those who were repressed by the stamp "enemy of the people" were kept in special children's institutions. From August 15, 1937 to January 1939, 25,342 children were separated from their families by Union, of which 22,427 under the age of 15 were disbanded to orphanages and local kindergartens under the people's Commissariat of Education. Of these, 1,909 were in Moscow, 2,915 were returned to families to feed others. Children whose age was above 15 years were considered "socially dangerous", imprisoned and sentenced.

While the women prisoners in Karaganda camp were serving the sentence, 1,507 had children, these children were born on the basis of rape."³

In conclusion, the policy of the great massacre of the Soviet government, which carried out colonial policy in the country for more than 70 years, in 1937-38, caused the untimely shooting of tens of thousands of Valiant and passionate, selfless children of the motherland. It is a pity that a lot of Science, which was exiled and shot as a result of a large policy of destruction, has a deep knowledge and worldview that adds a lot to the development of Science, and has a negative impact on the formation of the Renaissance era for today.

In memory of the March and Noble Children of our country, as the most pressing issue of the day in the early years of independence, in this regard, on the initiative of our first president Islam Abduganievich, on August 31, 2002, certain works were carried out on the formation of the scientific exposition of the museum, organized in the memorial complex "memory of martyrs", many times were searched for samples of press publications, and they took a place in the museum's exposition. In all regions, sections of the Museum of victims of repression were opened. New books dedicated to victims of repression are being created and the pure name of our ancestors is justified.

³Акромов А, Муратова Т. Озодлик йўлидаги кураш ёшлар учун ибрат мактаби. [//https://parliament.gov.uz/uz/events/opinion/31901/](https://parliament.gov.uz/uz/events/opinion/31901/)

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